

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Dynamic Latch-up/Latching Current Protection ASIC (LUCA)</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA10-352</i>
General application	<i>Space, COTS</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Thierry Delmot, nSilition srl</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>n.a.</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>7 to 9 of April 2025 (beam time: April 8, 14h to 22h)</i>
Facility	<i>GANIL</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>8 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

A dynamic latch-up detector/protector and current limitation ASIC (LUCA) has been implemented in silicon. A first prototype (first silicon) has been manufactured. This ASIC is beneficial to the space industry. Other available latch-up protection solutions do not provide that large variety of features and dynamic range. The LUCA integrates the protection into a smaller footprint and at a lower cost. This allows the application to deploy the protection and the supply monitoring/control features at several levels of the hardware.

The LUCA can be used with or without a micro-controller. It is possible to incorporate the LUCA into low-complexity space craft. It reduces the disadvantages associated with using standard integrated devices (COTS) in hardware exposed to space radiation.

The objective of the experiment was to carry out a first campaign of SEE tests on the first silicon prototype of the LUCA (LUCA v1.0). The main goal was to have a first assessment of the effects of heavy ions on the functional behavior and the robustness of the device.

Experiment test report

The measurements have been carried out at the GANIL facility (Caen, France) using the ^{129}Xe ion at a charge state of 46^+ and an energy of 49.6 MeV/u. As the LUCA is implemented on a SOI manufacturing process, using ions having high penetration range is increasing the probability to detect undesired SEE effects. That increases the coverage of the experiment.

The history of the campaign is summarized in the following table:

08/04/2025	
12h00	
13h00	

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14h00	
15h00	Installation nSilitation
16h00	<i>Runs 200 to 216</i>
17h00	
18h00	
19h00	
20h00	<i>Runs 217 to 242</i>
21h00	
22h00	Dismantling nSilitation
23h00	

Table 1: history of the test campaign (courtesy from GANIL's team)

1) Description of the test setup

A test setup was already in use at nSilitation before the confirmation of the support of RADNEXT for the tests. As described in the RADNEXT proposal, the setup is made by interconnecting instruments and generic reusable boards with the loadboard designed depending on the DUT¹. This assembly is controlled by the test software running on a PC (Figure 1).

¹ DUT = Design Under Test. The ASIC to be tested in this case.
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Figure 1: architecture of the test setup for the LUCA

The picture (*Figure 2*) here below presents the test setup as assembled and controlled during some characterization tests done in the lab of nSilitation, prior to this SEE test campaign.

Figure 2: setup as configured in the lab of nSilitation.

Due to the specific configuration of the particle exposition zone of the GANIL, a new version of the loadboard has been designed. The changes are allowing the compatibility with the fixtures of the exposition zone: connectors must have specific positions; shielding must be added (*Figure 3*), ...

Figure 3: new version of the loadboard, specific for the GANIL

The modular architecture (*Figure 1*) of the setup has limited the needed changes. The use of generic boards facilitates the interface with the instruments and the test software. The four photos here under are showing the setup at GANIL before and during installation. Bottom right is the control computer in the control room (small black box on the right of the rightest screen).

Figure 4: test setup at GANIL. Setup at different moments of installation. Test computers in the control room.

2) Irradiation plan

An irradiation plan has been laid-out before the experiment. This test plan has been programmed and debugged upfront. It covers all the functionalities of the LUCA, its behaviour from the point-of-view of the user. It is required that the functionalities of the device are not changing or malfunctioning as a consequence of an SEE. Some of the planned tests are also checking critical circuits more closely: the bandgap reference voltage generator, the charge pump of the internal DC/DC converter (floating voltage generator) and the main switch while in ON state, including its resistivity (RON). Table 2 here below summarizes the tests that were planned and their coverage in terms of SEE.

Test name	SEU	SEL	SEB ²	SEGR	SET
Standby and SEU 0xAA, supplied by VDD	X	X	X	X	X
Standby and SEU 0x55, supplied by IN	X	X	X	X	X
Standby and SEU 0x00, supplied by VDD	X	X	X	X	X
Standby and SEU 0xFF, supplied by IN	X	X	X	X	X
Main switch at ON state³ with low current, supplied by IN	X	X		X	X

² Coverage of SEB and SEGR has to be reviewed against bias condition of the main switch. Next campaign should seek to use the conditions that will maximize the risk of SEB and/or SEGR.

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Main switch at ON state with high current, supplied by VDD	X	X	X	X	X
Low current limit⁴, supplied by IN	X	X		X	X
High current limit⁴, supplied by VDD	X	X	X	X	X
Switching the main switch on and off while it is beamed	X			X	X
Initialization using sensor (TOV resistor of 360k)	X	X			X
Initialization using sensor (TOV resistor of 30k)	X	X			X
Initialization using sensor (no resistor)	X	X			X
Initialization using sensor (only TOV resistor)	X	X			X
Effect of SETs on SPI, test 1	X	X			X
Effect of SETs on SPI, test 2	X	X			X
Oscillator stability		X			X
Scan chain	X	X			X
OTP check	X	X			
Start Delay	X	X			
LU event delay	X	X			
Bandgap SETs		X			X
RON		X		X	X
CHPMP LDO (IN)		X			X
CHPMP load regulation		X			X
Daisy chain test	X	X			X

Table 2: summary of the SEE irradiation plan

The choice of the LET to be used for a given test is following a decision tree that is provided in the Figure 5 here under. Many of the tests listed in Table 2 have been run for different value of LET. If not, the test has been at least run at the highest LET that was possible to reach without tilting the board: 64.29 MeV*cm²/mg.

Figure 5: LET decision tree, compliant with the LETs that are available at the test facility.

Another set of tests that focuses on the blocks constituting the internal power management unit (PMU) was prepared. It was not used finally. More beam time was needed to carry out these block level tests. Their priority was lower than the functional tests, the reason why it was not possible to execute them during this test campaign.

3) Main outcomes of the tests.

3.1) LET of 42.17MeV*cm²/mg:

The first tests were done with particles having a LET of 42,17 Mev*cm²/mg (top of the LET decision tree

³ This is the main switch state that is in effect during the POWER GOOD state of the LUCA (cf. datasheet).

⁴ This is the main switch state that is in effect during the start-up phase (when powering up a load).

of Figure 5). These first tests were looking directly for the occurrence of major impairments like SEU on the control registers, SET on the supply voltages generated internally, SEB/SEGR on the main switch, SEL on IOs or on the main supply pin, ... No specific event could be recorded using this LET, even by increasing the fluence so that the beam time per experiment was always higher than 2min 30sec.

3.2) LET of 64.29MeV*cm²/mg:

The absence of observable events using the initial LET made us decide quickly to increase it to 64.29 MeV*cm²/mg. And to keep the fluence of each test at level so that long enough beam time are achieved (fluence of more than 2M particles was used, generally 3M particles was used).

These test conditions allowed to observe different events. Among all the different types of events, only one had an impact on the functional behaviour of the chip. Its probability of occurrence (efficient section) is very limited however. Here below is a summary of the observations.

3.2.1) SETs not having any damageable or annoying impact

Different SETs are observable at different moments and on different internal nodes of the chip. These nodes are observable thanks to tests accesses that have been provisioned during the design of the LUCA (DFT). Sometimes, an SET is also observable on one pin of the chip. We were not able to record any evidence that these SETs are impacting the functional behaviour of the chip. The Figure 6 hereunder illustrates this by showing one SET occurring on the internal voltage generated by the bandgap reference voltage generator (blue trace). And the same SET being “wiped-out” on the actual output voltage of the reference voltage generator block (red trace). This voltage is used by at different places in the chip and is thus critical. The absence of SET on the output node is the consequence of the hardening techniques by design that have been put in place in the LUCA.

Figure 6: SET on the bandgap voltage generator (blue trace) not propagated outside of the sub-block (red trace).

3.2.2) No SEU observed

No single SEU event was detected on the configuration registers of the device. This is validating the triplication technique put in place in the different functionalities implemented in various digital blocks of the LUCA. The SPI communication was also always working as expected under beaming. Also, no other erratic behavior was observed during any other experiment ran during the campaign. This looks to indicate that no SEU occurs on any flip-flops participating to the implementation of the internal state-machines or control functionalities of the chip.

A scan chain test mode has also been implemented in the silicon (DFT). This test mode allows to bypass the triplication of the logic cones and to observe individually any possible upset of the memory point of each flip-flop implemented in the design. The scan chain test allowed to demonstrate that each hardened flip-flop is immune to any SEU up to the maximum used LET (62.9 MeV*cm²/mg). Only some standard non-hardened flip-flops, used ON PURPOSE at some places in the LUCA, were affected by SEUs (these SEUs are not critical). These tests are validating the hardening techniques applied on the digital library developed by nSilitation and used in the LUCA.

3.2.3) No SEL observed

A latch-up detection board was connected to any supplies delivered to the LUCA at any time. From the perspective of the user, there are only two possible supply pins on the LUCA (IN or VDD). But some test modes are provisioning the possibility to supply a specific block from a dedicated power source. In that case, this test supply was also subject to latch-up monitoring. The latch-up detection board is displayed on the picture (*Figure 7*) here under.

Figure 7: The home-made generic latch-up detection board used on the radiation tests setups of nSilitation.

The experiment at GANIL allowed us to come to the observation that the latch-up board was not behaving exactly as we wanted. In some case, we had to raise the threshold level in order to avoid a parasitic disconnection of the supply. This limitation is somewhat masking the possibility to be able to detect micro latch-ups. These ones can build-up over time before that some functional impairment is really visible. This latch-up detector has to be improved for the next time. From that moment it will be evident that no SEL occurred at any time.

3.2.3) No SEB or SEGR observed

The main switch of the LUCA is gigantic (at the level of the silicium) since it must be able to drive 2A with a very low RON. Consequently, this transistor is highly exposed to the effect of heavy ions. Various design techniques have been used in the LUCA to protect this main transistor from SEB or SEGR.

Different bias configurations of the main switch have been tried in different test scenarios during this SEE irradiation campaign. Some were made to increase the susceptibility of the main switch to SEGR, others to SEB. Glitches have been observed on the output pin controlled by the main switch. This pin is powering the load of the application. The behavior of this pin is critical. Manifestations of SETs have been observed. But no single destructive effect has been observed during the whole test campaign. Other test conditions were putting the main switch in OFF state. There, it was important to verify that the switch stayed well OFF. That no supply glitches could pass through the main switch and inadvertently power the load. Or that suddenly the state of the main switch flips to ON (even for a limited time) although it was not the purpose to supply the load. Finally, a specific test was switching ON-OFF-ON the main switch as many times as possible while the beam was enabled. No unexpected behavior was observed for all the beam runs that have tested.

It must be also noted that the charge pump DC/DC converter, another block sensible to SEB/SEGR, did not show any sign of destruction or degradation too.

The two figures here under are illustrating some single event effects observed on the main switch.

Figure 8: SET (left) and another SEE (right) observed on the OUT pin as the main switch is exposed to ^{129}Xe ions

A deeper analysis of the SEB and SEGR test conditions is however an action programmed at our side. It is sure that the test scenarios were generating conditions promoting the susceptibility to SEB and SEGR of the main switch and the charge pump. However, a deeper analysis must be done in the coming weeks, certainly before a second SEE campaign on the chip is carried-out. It is important to be sure that the worst conditions are actually tested. We have in fact to search to the worst-case condition that the user can ever put on the chip considering SEB and SEGR susceptibility.

3.2.3) Observation of sporadic unwanted RESET of the chip

Although the LUCA has been found to be very robust to a lot of different kinds of SEEs, some cases showing an unwanted reset of the chip have been detected during the whole 8 h of experiment.

It is sure that we were not able to observe any unwanted RESET once the LET of the particles was set to 55 MeV*cm²/mg or below. They occur only once the LET is set to 62.9. Moreover, the efficient area is rather low: 5 RESET events have been observed over a total fluence of 40.2M ions used at this LET during the whole campaign. Hence the efficient area is estimated to be around 1.24*10⁻⁷ (at LET of 62.9). The threshold is standing somewhere between 55 and 62.9 MeV*cm²/mg.

Some test configuration allows to access to the RESETN output pin of the PMU of the LUCA. This is the internal reset node in the chip (the chip has no external user controllable RESET pin). The PMU is designed so that it raises the internal RESETN signal (i.e. disables the reset state) once all supplies are reaching their minimal value. And going back to reset state in case one of these conditions is not met. This is a wanted behavior. However, it looks here at first glance⁵ that a RESET is occurring although all supplies are in good shape.

From the moment a first unwanted RESET was detected in a test, the configuration of many forthcoming tests were quickly modified in a way that the voltage on the internal RESETN pin could be observed on one channel of the oscilloscope. Here below (Figure 9) are two examples of capture of an SET on the internal RESETN node of the chip. The one on the left is small enough to not trig any reset, the one on the right is deep enough (going to low state ($V \leq \sim V_{dd}/2$) for approximately 0.6 μsec) to possibly propagate through all flip-flops.

Figure 9: SETs observed on the internal RESETN node of the LUCA

It is possible to observe that the chip has reset by another means than by checking the voltage of the internal RESETN node. For all the tests done during this campaign, at least a few internal registers of the LUCA must be programmed to values different than the default values after reset. This programming is done during the initialization phase of each test, before that the beam of ions is applied to the chip. Downloading the value of all registers after the end of the beam time (after that the wanted fluence has been reached) and comparing with the values after initialization (before the beam is started) allows to check for any possible reset and any SEU on a configuration register.

⁵ Making this statement more solid requires to run a series of tests on the PMU that we did not had the time to run during this campaign. We were just able to monitor the supplies we provided from the outside.

Luckily, this “before-after” crosscheck was anyway programmed by default for each test in preparation of the test campaign. This is allowing to maximize the coverage of the detection of potential SEU on the configuration registers. It is checked on any test of the whole irradiation campaign, in the background of other observations. It was therefore very easy to use it for detection for any unwanted reset.

Doing correlations between the observation of any voltage glitch on the internal RESETN node of the chip and the comparison of the state of the registers before and after the beam time allowed us to conclude that there is not always a direct correlation between the two events:

- Sometimes a RESET is observed by “before-after” inspection of the configuration register while no deep enough SET has been observed on the internal RESETN node of the chip.
- Sometimes a deep enough glitch is observed on the internal RESETN node of the chip while the inspection of the registers demonstrates that the chip did not go the reset state.

This correlation exercise just tends to indicate that the internal reset of the chip seems to be due to a SET occurring at another place than the node that can be observed through the test access.

Other tests are possible. They will improve the observation of what is occurring in the PMU. However, we did not have the time to carry-out these tests before the end of the time allocated to nSilition.

The occurrence of the unwanted RESET events is one of the most important reasons to make us believe that another SEE test campaign will be needed in the coming months. We need to improve the coverage of the tests in SEE. We need to test more than the bandgap output voltage. There are other blocks in the PMU participating to the verification of the correctness of the supply voltages.

4) Summary of the results

4.1) Result table

Table 3 here below is summarizing the main observations that could be recorded during this SEE campaign.

Test name	Status
Standby and SEU 0xAA, supplied by VDD	<i>SETs observed. The device resets during one run. No SEU observed. No unexpected powering of the output observed</i>
Standby and SEU 0x55, supplied by IN	<i>SETs observed. No SEU observed. No reset, no unexpected powering of the output observed</i>
Standby and SEU 0x00, supplied by VDD	<i>SETs observed. The device resets during one run. No SEU observed. No unexpected powering of the output observed</i>
Standby and SEU 0xFF, supplied by IN	<i>SETs observed. No reset, no unexpected powering of the output observed</i>
ON state with low current, supplied by IN	<i>SETs observed. The device resets during one run. No SEU observed.</i>
ON state with high current, supplied by VDD	<i>SETs observed. No reset and no SEU observed.</i>
Low current limit, supplied by IN	<i>400kHz waveforms captured for a short time on the output pin powering the load. No further consequence. No reset and no SEU observed.</i>
High current limit, supplied by VDD	<i>SETs observed. No reset and no SEU observed.</i>
Switching the main switch on and off while it is beamed	<i>The device resets during one of the multiple runs.</i>

Initialization using sensor (TOV resistor of 360k)	<i>Skipped. Loadboard hardware problem detected.</i>
Initialization using sensor (TOV resistor of 30k)	<i>Skipped. Loadboard hardware problem detected.</i>
Initialization using sensor (no resistor)	<i>Skipped. Loadboard hardware problem detected.</i>
Initialization using sensor (only TOV resistor)	<i>Skipped. Loadboard hardware problem detected.</i>
Effect of SETs on SPI, test 1	<i>No SET seen during SPI communication. The LUCA resets during one run. The behavior of the SPI interface just after reset stays consistent with the protocol.</i>
Effect of SETs on SPI, test 2	<i>Skipped. Not enough events seen during the detection of SETs on SPI test 1.</i>
Oscillator stability	<i>Signal capture must be improved. Results have been most probably subject to aliasing effect.</i>
Scan chain	<i>SEU seen on NONRH flipflops only. Hardened flipflops are not subject to SEUs.</i>
OTP check	<i>Skipped. The testability of the OTP on the LUCA must be improved for SEE tests. This requires a design change for the next tape-out of LUCA</i>
Start Delay	<i>Skipped. No time.</i>
LU event delay	<i>Skipped. No time.</i>
Bandgap SETs	<i>SET seen on the internal node. The SET is not observed on the output voltage distributed in the chip.</i>
RON	<i>Skipped. No time.</i>
CHPMP LDO (IN)	<i>Skipped. No time.</i>
CHPMP load regulation	<i>Skipped. No time.</i>
Daisy chain test	<i>Skipped. No time.</i>

Table 3: summary of the main results recorded during the SEE test campaign of April 2025

5) Lessons learned during this test campaign

5.1) Catching all possible SETs

This campaign made us think about the phenomenon of SET once more. The non full correlation between the observation of SETs made on the RESETN pin and the effective resets of the LUCA started a debate within the test team of nSilition. At the time of the edition of this report, it is now believed that a correct observation of all SETs requires a more specialized setting of the trigger on the oscilloscope. And the need to use an oscilloscope that has advanced/complex trigger detection capabilities. This has to be reviewed before the next campaign.

5.2) Clock tests

The sampling rate of the oscilloscope used for the clock tests must be much higher than the Nyquist rate.

5.3) Unwanted resets

Another SEE test campaign must be executed with this version of the LUCA before starting any design

iteration (towards LUCA v2.0). A focus shall be placed on doing more observations around the internal nodes of the PMU. A dedicated review of the schematic shall be done in order to identify possible weaknesses and to establish the best method to observe them. Other tests configuration allowing accesses to the internals have been provisioned in the LUCA.

5.4) Speed of the test setup

For a reason that still needs to be deeply investigated, the test setup can take up to 1 min to get through the initialization phase (the preparation done before that the beam can be started)! For this campaign, the setup is powered off completely before the start of any new test. In this way, it is sure that the setup is always at the wanted state before the beam is started. However, it seems that some supply voltage sources controlled by the test program are slow to stabilize. One should improve the programming of the initialization phase. To speed it up before the next campaign. For instance, the latch-up detection board (*Figure 7*) can be used to power-off (and reset) the chip without the need to power-off completely the setup. This will allow to increase the effective utilization time of the beam.

5.5) Latch-up detection board

The latch-up detection board (*Figure 7*) must be reviewed in depth and more probably the design has to be improved before returning to the next SEE tests campaign. This must be 100% sure that there is evidence that no latch-up occurred in any circumstances.

5.6) Testability for SEE (DFSEE)

The testability of the LUCA is already very good. However, the observation window of SEEs on the OTP memory is much too small. This has to be improved. This will require another tape-out of the LUCA, which will not be possible before the second SEE test campaign on the LUCA. Doing this second SEE test campaign before any design change is a sensible investment however. Indeed, other parameters have to be observed before investing in a redesign of the chip. The coverage of the tests done until now is not high enough.

5.7) Other variants of SEB and SEGR test conditions

Specific variants of the SEB and SEGR test conditions have to be developed. This to make sure the worst-case conditions in terms of SEB and SEGR are created around the main switch. This will increase the coverage on the efficiency of the protections implemented in the design.

5.8) Overall test coverage

The tests that were not done by lack of time must be executed in a next campaign. The initialization time of the setup shall be reduced before that a second SEE test campaign is done.

6) Conclusion

This first SEE test campaign done on the LUCA is successful and allowed to collect very encouraging results. A second campaign is however highly recommended:

- It has been observed that NO event impacting the functionality of the LUCA occurs at $LET \leq 55 \text{MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$.
- Testing at LET of $62,9 \text{MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$ allows to observe an annoying unwanted reset of the LUCA. The efficient section of this event is low. The reasons must be investigated however. Even at low probability, this event can be a reason for future customers to NOT adopt the LUCA as the solution for protecting their COTS electronic devices from latch-up events.
- The way SELs are monitored is not good enough to provide solid evidence that no latch-up or micro latch-up ever occurred. Although we are convinced it is the case. The latch-up detector board has to be improved before that a second test campaign is carried-out.
- The speed of the initialization of the tests has to be improved, in order to improve the utilization

of the allocated time.

- Lessons have been learned on how to improve the SEE testability in any of our future radiation hardened chip design (including the next update of the LUCA).

It will be beneficial for the LUCA product development project and for the continuous improvement of the expertise of the team to run a second test campaign on this version of the LUCA.

nSilitation will introduce a new request for the truly appreciated and useful support of RADNEXT in financing the utilization time of a heavy ion facility. The help of the RADNEXT project is essential to our team and to our project to scale-up the business of nSilitation. Thank you for your support in this campaign subject to this report and in any upcoming one!

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other: improvement of the SEE test setups designed by nSilitation	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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